

Calibrated Oscilloscope Measurements for System-Level Characterization of Weakly Nonlinear Sources*

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Abstract — We present a technique to characterize and correct for linear and weakly nonlinear distortion introduced by the nonideal response of a wideband, high-frequency modulated-signal source. The magnitude and phase relationships between frequency components in a measured modulated signal are maintained by use of a calibrated equivalent-time sampling oscilloscope. The nonidealities of the oscilloscope and other components of the measurement system are corrected during post processing. Determination of the uncertainties in the measurement allows a user to identify magnitude and phase distortion in the generated waveform.

Index Terms — Digitally modulated signals, nonlinear measurements, oscilloscope, wireless system.

I. INTRODUCTION

To utilize wideband signal generators for design or test of wireless communication components and systems, it is critical to be able to separate distortion introduced by the components under test from distortion introduced by the source itself. Characterizing distortion from a wideband, high-speed, high-frequency source can be complicated by the fact that many wideband vector receivers employ high-speed samplers, amplifiers, and other nonideal circuit components similar to those used in the sources. Thus, the nonideal response of the vector receiver used to calibrate the source may lead to non-negligible distortion when measuring modulated signals.

We introduce a technique based on the use of a calibrated equivalent-time sampling oscilloscope to measure and correct for both linear and weakly nonlinear distortion exhibited by a wideband modulated-signal generator. We demonstrate the technique by correcting for the in-band distortion of signals having a 1.2 GHz modulation bandwidth at center frequencies of both 4 GHz and 44 GHz. The technique discussed here could also be used to characterize intermodulation distortion or harmonic distortion for such signals. We provide measurement examples and associated uncertainties.

Wideband modulated-signal sources are often based on arbitrary-waveform generators (AWGs) that incorporate high-speed digital-to-analog converters (DACs) [1-4]. Interleaving signals from multiple DACs is sometimes used to increase the effective sampling rate. The high sampling rate enables users

to reproduce electrically a rapidly varying digitally modulated signal. However, DACs, especially those operating at or near the state of the art in sampling speed, may introduce errors into the modulated signal including DAC quantization errors, noise, nonlinearity and imbalance (if interleaved). When incorporated into a signal generator, other components, including amplifiers, switches and frequency converters, may introduce distortion as well. Due to nonlinearities associated with many of these components, the amount of distortion present at the output of the signal generator often depends on the peak-to-average power ratio and/or bandwidth of the signal to be generated. The large number of potentially nonlinear components, along with the dependence of the nonlinearity on the input signal makes the development of a model of the signal generator's nonideal response quite complicated. The simple "black-box" approach we describe here is straightforward and can be used to reduce in-band distortion caused by the linear and mildly nonlinear response of DAC-based modulated-signal sources.

II. CALIBRATED OSCILLOSCOPE MEASUREMENTS

Key to our technique for characterizing the distortion at the output of a modulated-signal source is the use of a calibrated receiver. For modulated-signal measurements, the acquired signal must maintain the real-time, vector relationship between frequency components. While maintaining the relationship between magnitude components may be accomplished with a power-based instrument such as a spectrum analyzer, maintaining the phase relationships must be accomplished with a vector receiver. Instruments such as vector signal analyzers (VSAs) are often used for this purpose because of their ability to measure thousands of frequency components in a bandpass signal on a fine frequency grid. However, VSAs currently exhibit modulation bandwidths on the order of 200 MHz, which may be insufficient for the gigahertz-wide modulation bandwidths envisioned for future millimeter-wave communication systems [5].

Present-day equivalent-time sampling oscilloscopes have measurement bandwidths of up to 100 GHz. However, they may present a reduced dynamic range when compared to a VSA. Also, equivalent-time sampling oscilloscopes must be presented with periodic signals. Neither of these restrictions presents a problem for the application discussed here: the dynamic range of the modulated-signal source is at least an

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order of magnitude lower than the oscilloscope, due to hardware issues such as quantization noise introduced by the DACs [4]. As well, periodic signals, including multisines and digitally-modulated pseudo-random bit sequences (PRBS), are often used for wireless system test. Thus, the use of a periodic signal will place the source into its normal operating state when it is characterized.

To separate the distortion introduced by the source from that of the receiver, we used a calibrated sampling oscilloscope [6-8] to measure the magnitude and phase response of an AWG-based, wideband modulated-signal source. As shown in Fig. 1 and discussed in more detail in [9], the source was configured to generate modulated signals at both microwave intermediate frequencies (IF) and at millimeter-wave radio frequencies (RF). For the example discussed here, the IF was 4 GHz and the RF was 44 GHz, which were both measured simultaneously by our 50-GHz sampling oscilloscope.

Figure 1: Block diagram of an AWG-based modulated-signal source that generates wideband signals at both IF (4 GHz) and RF (44 GHz). The source was characterized with an equivalent-time sampling oscilloscope at both the IF and RF reference planes. Note that use of an SMA cable for the IF path would be acceptable.

Several corrections to the oscilloscope measurements are necessary to accurately characterize the signal emanating from the modulated-signal source. These have been discussed in prior publications [e.g., 9] and include: (1) correction of jitter, drift, and systematic errors in the oscilloscope’s time base [10, 11]; (2) correction for the oscilloscope’s internal response [12]; and (3) impedance-mismatch correction of the oscilloscope’s sampling head and the modulated-signal source at the reference planes indicated in Fig. 1. For mismatch correction at millimeter-wave frequencies, we must include adapters on the appropriate side of the reference plane, such as the 2.4 mm female-to-female adapter used to connect the source to the sampling oscilloscope (and to other instruments to be calibrated, such as a VSA). Also, time-domain averaging is carried out to improve the dynamic range of the measurement to approximately 60 dB at 45 GHz.

Denoting the oscilloscope’s complex frequency response as $H(f)$, and the frequency-dependent impedance mismatch of the source and oscilloscope as $\Gamma(f)_{\text{source}}$ and $\Gamma(f)_{\text{scope}}$, respectively,

the corrected measurement of the voltage $v(f)_{\text{source}}$ at the output of the modulated-signal source may be given by [13]

$$v_{\text{source}} = v_{\text{source,raw}} \left(\frac{1 - \Gamma_{\text{source}} \Gamma_{\text{scope}}}{H} \right), \quad (1)$$

where the frequency dependence of all quantities has been suppressed.

From the corrections discussed above, we are able to provide a complete error analysis for our oscilloscope measurements. This allows us to separate the distortion caused by the oscilloscope from that of the modulated-signal source.

III. THE RESPONSE OF A MODULATED-SIGNAL SOURCE

The calibrated oscilloscope is used to characterize and correct for the nonideal response of the modulated-signal source. Once the linear and nonlinear components of the system response have been identified, the signal that is uploaded to the AWG is then corrected for, or “predistorted,” by this response. For the work presented here, we used a simple iterative “black-box” approach based on measurements of the system response, as illustrated in Figure 2. While more sophisticated methods based on nonlinear models of the system response also could be used to increase the efficiency of the characterization procedure [14, 15], our focus is instead on the measurements and calibrations needed to accurately perform predistortion. The first iteration removes the linear transfer function of the AWG (IF) and frequency converter subsystem, if used (RF). Subsequent iterations remove the weakly nonlinear response of these components. An improved estimate of the system response is extracted in each iteration.

Figure 2: The iterative procedure for identifying the linear and weakly nonlinear system response of an AWG-based modulated-signal source.

The procedure is straightforward, involving only simple frequency-domain operations on the measured, uploaded and ideal signal. However, to maximize the accuracy of the measurement, the user must consider carefully the time-

synchronization of the signal in order to minimize time-to-frequency-domain transformation artifacts [9].

We illustrate the use of our measurement-based characterization-and-predistortion procedure with an example. The waveform in our example was a multisine waveform intended to represent a 64-QAM modulated signal. The multisine consists of 1023 frequency components covering a modulation bandwidth of approximately 1.2 GHz. We measured the signal at 44 GHz on Channel 1 and at 4 GHz on Channel 2 of the oscilloscope.

Figures 3(a) and (b) show the magnitude spectrum of the modulated signal. The solid black lines represent the ideal signal that was initially loaded into the AWG. The red dots represent the measured signal and the green dashed lines correspond to the AWG input, after predistortion by the method shown in Fig. 2. In Fig. 3(a), the initial measured signal deviates significantly from the ideal signals. In Fig. 3(b), after four iterations, the response has been identified, the input has been predistorted, and the measured signal is much improved. We saw a similar result for the 4 GHz waveform, not shown here in order to save space.

Figure 3: Frequency spectrum of a 1023-tone multisine designed to represent a digitally modulated signal. The solid black curve is the ideal signal, the red dots are the 44 GHz measurements (downconverted to 4 GHz in post processing) and the green dashed line represents the input to the AWG that has been predistorted to correct for the nonideal response of the signal generator. (a) Initial measurement and first predistortion iteration. (b) After four iterations.

In Figure 4, we show the phase error corresponding to the difference between the ideal signal that was initially loaded into the AWG and the oscilloscope-measured phases for the (a) RF and (b) IF signals. The measured phases were time-aligned with the detrending procedure outlined in [16] before subtraction. We see that after the first iteration, the phase error is greatly reduced, from tens of degrees to a few degrees. Subsequent iterations reduce the phase error even more.

Figure 4: Phase error resulting from the nonideal response of the signal generator. The original, unpredistorted phase error is shown, along with those corresponding to four additional predistortion steps (PreD1 – PreD4). (a) 44 GHz waveform. (b) 4 GHz waveform.

IV. MEASUREMENT UNCERTAINTY

An uncertainty analysis was conducted with the NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework [17, 18], which keeps track of all uncertainty mechanisms in the measurement plus their correlations. Our uncertainty analysis includes measurement errors from the correction of the nonideal oscilloscope response, mismatch correction, as well as repeatability. In all, more than 640 error mechanisms were considered, including a wide array of parameters from the pin depth of the calibration standards, to effects of cable bend, to optical parameters for the electro-optic sampling system. For the measurements presented here, the major sources of uncertainty were related to the repeatability of the five

waveforms that were averaged before transformation to the frequency domain.

Uncertainties related to the measured 44 GHz signal are shown in Fig. 5, where we see 95 % confidence intervals less than (a) 0.1 mV in the magnitude and (b) $\sim 3^\circ$ in the phase, with lower phase uncertainty in the main passband of the signal. Distortion emanating from the modulated-signal source can be characterized to within these values.

Figure 5: Measurement uncertainty, represented by the 95 % confidence interval, in a 1.2 GHz wide, digitally modulated 64-QAM signal. In (a), the blue dots represent the 95 % confidence interval, in decibels. The inset shows an expanded view from 44.2 to 44.4 GHz. In (b), the 95% confidence interval of the signal phase is shown above and below the phase error.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented a simple “black-box” approach that can be used to characterize the linear and mildly nonlinear response of DAC-based modulated-signal sources. Once the response is known, predistortion of the signal that is input to the AWG will reduce in-band distortion of the signal generated by the source.

The technique may be used to characterize the mildly nonlinear distortion from a number of instruments and components. It could be used, for example, to populate a look-up table, if the signal source was used to generate a limited set of output signals. Because the technique provides an independent calibration of a signal source, the calibrated

source may then be used for subsequent calibration of vector receivers used in wireless system design and test.

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